

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

ANALYSIS OF THE FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF VIRAL NEUROINFECTIONS TO OPTIMIZE THE DIAGNOSTICS OF ACUTE VIRAL ENCEPHALITIS AT THE EARLY STAGES OF HOSPITALIZATION

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Annotation: In this work, 14 cases of acute viral encephalitis in children aged 7 months were studied and analyzed. – 16 years (mean age 5.8 years $\pm$ 1.4). The aim of our work was to analyze the features of the course of viral neuroinfections in order to optimize the diagnosis of acute viral encephalitis in the early stages of hospitalization.

Key words: viral neuroinfections, course features

Relevance. The incidence of viral encephalitis varies from 3.9 to 7.5 per 100,000 child population *1+. According to WHO data, 75% of all cases of viral CNS lesions (meningitis, encephalitis) occur in children under 14 years of age *2+. For children's age, this pathology is characterized by a special severity, a high frequency of neurological complications of a debilitating nature and high mortality *3+. The severity of the course of encephalitis is due to the necrotic nature of the process with the formation of foci of decay of the mog substance followed by bone formation, especially in the weight lobes of the mog *4+. According to the WHO, diseases caused by the herpes simplex virus (HSV) rank second (15.8%) after the

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group (35.8%) as the number of deaths from viral infections *5+. Often, infectious lesions of the nervous system are the cause of neonatal seizures in 3-17% of cases. Conversely, neonatal seizures may be the first symptom of an inflammatory disease. Also, intracranial vasculitis in children, as a prelude to hemorrhagic stroke, is more often detected by bacterial meningitis or viral encephalitis *6+. The case of complete recovery of patients with encephalitis caused by VOG-1 is rare. Acute meningoencephalitis caused by VOG-2 is accompanied by high mortality (50-80%) and development of a severe CNS defect in the above patients.

Purpose: to analyze the features of the course of viral neuroinfections to optimize the diagnosis of acute viral encephalitis in the early stages of hospitalization. To give a clinical description of acute viral encephalitis. To study and characterize the neurological manifestations of acute viral encephalitis and their complications. Assess the etiological and age structure of acute viral encephalitis.

Material and methods. In this work, 14 cases of acute viral encephalitis in children aged 7 months were studied and analyzed. – 16 years (mean age 5.8 years $\pm$ 1.4), Statistical analysis was carried out using Excel and Statistica 7 programs.

Results and its discussion. The age structure given in this article corresponds to the literature data. Such a distribution can be explained by the imperfection of the protective mechanisms in children of early and preschool age and the tendency to generalize the inflammatory process in the CNS [3]. Among the sick were 10 boys (71%), 4 girls (29%). A retrospective evaluation of 14 clinical cases was carried out. First of all, in order to assess the alertness of primary care physicians regarding neuroinfections, the diagnoses of the referral for these diseases were studied. gastroenteritis, neuroinfection was suspected in 5 children (36%) upon

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referral, 2 children (14%) were admitted without diagnosis. Most of the children were hospitalized on the 2-3rd day from the onset of the disease, however, there were cases of later hospitalization, in particular, two patients were hospitalized on the 6th day of illness. These data may indicate the polymorphism of the clinical manifestations of encephalitis, which does not allow us to suspect a neuroinfection in the early stages of its development. The duration of hospitalization averaged 29 days, the maximum duration was 104 days. The etiological structure was as follows (Figure 1): in 5 (36%) cases, enterovirus nature (EVI) was confirmed, in 2 cases (14%) - herpes simplex virus (HSV) I, II types, in 1 case (7%) - Epstein-Barr virus, also in 1 case (7%), a viral association was detected (EVI, HSV). In addition, in 5 (36%) cases, the etiology was not established. To determine the pathogenic agent, PCR and ELISA methods were used, in 56% and 44%, respectively. According to the literature data, the following main syndromes can be distinguished in the clinical picture of the disease: intoxication syndrome with fever; syndrome of cerebral disorders; syndrome of disturbance of consciousness; convulsive syndrome; focal disorder syndrome. All of the above occurred in the cases we studied. In all cases, the disease debuted with the onset of headache and fever, i. with the manifestation of a general infectious syndrome and a syndrome of cerebral disorders. The minimum value of fever was 37.8 degrees, the maximum - 39.8 degrees, the average figures - 38.6. During the day, the above symptoms were accompanied by vomiting in 43% of cases (in 4 children (29%) - single, in 2 (14%) - repeated). Convulsive syndrome on the first day of the disease manifested itself in 5 children (36%), in total, during the course of the disease, secondary tonic-clonic convulsions with or without loss of consciousness were observed in 11

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children (79%). Impaired consciousness was observed in all patients, but had varying degrees of severity, from lethargy to coma (Glasgow Coma Scale score was 8). At the same time, in isolated cases, arousal and hallucinosis were observed. Meningeal symptoms were moderately expressed in 8 (57%) children. Focal disorders included motor aphasia (in 1 case), lower paraparesis with dysfunction of the pelvic organs (in 1 case), symptoms of cranial nerve damage (in 7 cases). In the study of the bioelectrical activity of the brain (in 10 patients), pathological types of EEG were recorded in all, namely, diffuse EEG changes with a predominance of delta activity (in 4 children), slow-wave activity of the delta-theta range (in 4 children), disorganization of the cortical rhythm with a predominance of theta rhythm, a tendency to hypersynchronization of the theta rhythm (in 1 child), amplitude predominance of alpha activity on one side (in 1 child). Changes in the CSF were characterized by pleocytosis in 71% of cases (in 10 children), while the average value of cytotosis was $65 \cdot 10^9/L$. There was a slight decrease in the level of chlorides (the minimum value was about 112 mmol/l, the average value was 119 mmol/l), an increase in the level of glucose (the average value was 4.07 mmol/l). The protein level in 50% of cases did not exceed 0.33 g/l.

Conclusions: In the clinic of acute viral encephalitis, convulsive syndrome came to the fore, both on the first day and throughout the entire period of illness. The main neurological symptoms were secondary generalized convulsive seizures, symptoms of focal lesions of the cranial nerves, residual psychoemotional disorders. Among the identified most common pathogens were viruses of the genus Enterovirus, $p < 0.01$. Acute viral encephalitis in children has a number of clinical and laboratory features, to some extent related to the age of the patient, the

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etiology of the disease, which requires further study, optimization of diagnostic protocols, therapy and prevention.

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